

Impact of Academic Anxiety on Academic Achievement of Class IXth Students: An Analysis (With Reference to Fatehgarh, Punjab)

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Abstract

This study was focused on to find out the impact of academic anxiety on the achievement of High school Govt and private schools' Students. For the purpose sample of total 120 students were selected randomly from 10 govt and 10 private schools of Fatehgarh Punjab. Using parameteric statistics this study was concluded that Private schools' Girls were significantly more anxious than government schools' girls towards their academic achievement rest high schools' students not differ significantly towards the effect of gender.

Keywords: Academic Anxiety, Achievement, Students, Fatehgarh, Punjab.

Introduction

Typically, anxiety can manifest as either state or trait anxiety. Trait anxiety represents a constant characteristic within an individual, whereas state anxiety is transient and triggered by specific environmental factors such as exams, accidents, or punishments. Academic anxiety, a subset of state anxiety, pertains to apprehension related to academic circumstances including teachers, subjects like mathematics and English, among others.

Anxiety poses challenges to task completion, as individuals may struggle to concentrate fully. Consequently, there's a common belief that anxiety hampers the learning process. However, this notion oversimplifies anxiety's impact, as it can either impede or facilitate learning.

Attention plays a crucial role in learning, with students requiring a level of "normal anxiety" to be receptive. In social settings devoid of such anxiety, children may display disregard for others' rights and emotions, becoming self-centered. Nevertheless, most children develop a degree of "normal anxiety," which contributes positively to social development by instilling self-control and consideration for others.

A 2016 report from the National Institute of Mental Health (NIMH, 1949) indicated that 30% of girls and 20% of boys among 6.3 million teenagers suffer from anxiety disorders. Education is among several contributing factors, with academic anxiety significantly impacting educational environments. The escalating aspirations of students toward prestigious professions intensify global academic competition, detrimentally affecting overall academic performance and mental well-being. Heightened expectations from various societal sources compel students into intense competitive environments, despite differences in cognitive abilities, socioeconomic status, stress coping mechanisms, and consistency in performance. Consequently, many students experience prolonged struggles in selecting suitable academic paths, driven by aspirations to excel in demanding entrance examinations such as those for Indian Administrative Services, medical sciences, and engineering.

Objectives

1. To study the effect of academic anxiety on academic achievement of the students.
2. To know the difference between the govt. schools' students and private school students with respect to the effect of academic anxiety on academic achievement.

Hypothesis

1. There will be no significant difference in Academic Anxiety level of Govt. School boys and Private School boys.
2. There will be no significant difference in Academic Anxiety level of Govt. School Girls and Private School Girls.
3. There will be no significant difference in academic Anxiety level of Govt. School Boys and Private School Girls.
4. There is no significant difference in Academic Anxiety level of Private School Boys and Private School Girls.
5. There is no significant difference in academic Anxiety level of total Boys and total Girls

Research Methodology:

Under survey research methodology sample of 120 students of class IX was drawn randomly from 10 high schools of Fatehgarh, Punjab. Academic Anxiety Scale for Children (AASC) by Dr. A.K. Singh and Dr. (Ms). A. Sengupta standardized tool has been used in this study.

Analysis and Interpretation

Hypothesis 1 :

"There will be no significant difference in Academic Anxiety level of Govt. School boys and Private School boys"

Group	N	Mean	Std. Devi	t-Value
Govt School Boys	30	11.9	2.65	0.10*
Private School Boys	30	11.83	2.58	

***Not Significant**

The value of t at 58 df and 0.05 level is 0.10 that was less than the accepted value. Hence it is not significant. So, the null hypothesis is accepted. It means there is no significant difference in Academic Anxiety level of Govt. School Boys and Private School Boys.

Hypothesis 2:

"There will be no significant difference in Academic Anxiety level of Govt. School Girls and Private School Girls"

Group	N	Mean	Std. Devi	t-Value
Govt School Girls	30	10.7	2.40	3.16*
Private School Girls	30	12.77	2.66	

***Significant**

The accepted value of t at 58 df and 0.05 level = 2.00. The value of t at 58 df and 0.01 level = 2.66. This value of calculated t is greater than the standard value. of t hence it is significant at both level and the difference in academic anxiety level of Govt. School Girls and Private Schools Girls is significant. So, the null hypothesis is rejected. It means that there is significant difference in academic anxiety level of Govt. School Girls and Private School girls.

Hypothesis 3 :

"There will be no significant difference in academic Anxiety level of Govt. School Boys and Private School Girls"

Group	N	Mean	Std. Devi	t-Value
Govt School Boys	30	11.9	2.65	1.27*
Private School Girls	30	12.77	2.66	

*Not Significant

The value of t at 58 df and 0.05 level = 2.00 The value of t at 58 df and 0.01 level = 2.66 respectively. The calculated valued t = 1.27 is less than these two values and hence is not significant. Therefore, there is no significant difference in academic anxiety level of Govt. School Boys and Private Schools Girls. Hence the null hypothesis no. 3 is accepted.

Hypothesis 4 :

"There is no significant difference in Academic Anxiety level of Private School Boys and Private School Girls"

Group	N	Mean	Std. Devi.	t-Value
Private School Boys	30	11.83	2.58	1.39
Private School girls	30	12.77	2.66	

*Not Significant

For df 58 the standard value of t at 0.05 level and 0.01 level of significance are 2.00 and 2.66 respectively. These low values are greater than the calculated value of t 1.39, hence this is not significant and thus the hypothesis 4 is accepted. It means there is no significant difference in academic Anxiety level of Private School Boys and Private School Girls.

Hypothesis 5 :

"There is no significant difference in academic Anxiety level of total Boys and total Girls"

Group	N	Mean	Std. Devi	t-Value
Boys	60	11.86	2.62	0.27
Girls	60	11.73	2.73	

*Not Significant

t-score are For df 118 the standard value of t at 0.05 level and 0.01 level of significance are 1.98 and 2.62 respectively. The calculated value of t = 0.27 is less than these low values, and hence it is not significant therefore the 5th hypothesis is accepted. Hence "There is no significant difference in academic Anxiety level of total Boys and total Girls"

Conclusion:

In today's school environment students are facing more challenges in their life. In early age of their life they are more aware for the betterment of their life and having high level of anxiety due to increased study work load that affect their academic achievement as well. This above study has shown high level of anxiety among Girls and boys too but gender does not affect academic achievement significantly and private schools' girls were found significantly more anxious than of their Govt schools Girls.

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